

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

Grant Agreement No. 870626

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v.03			

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Deliverable D 3.2

This deliverable represents the Survey questionnaire developed by Abeer Pervaiz and Joost Poort and the ensuing data set. The survey has been translated into 22 official EU languages and is targeted at artists belonging to a wide range of creative fields (authors, performers, designers, singers, musicians, dancers and more) within the EU. The survey has been distributed through different social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn, various social groups, websites and also via networking.

This document gives an overview of the participant data that has been collected till 16 February 2022 . The data provides both descriptive and visual information. Descriptive data concerning the response will be updated once the survey is closed. This document and the data set together form deliverable D3.2.

Following the descriptive participant data is the survey questionnaire. Each question statement represents a labeled value that is shown in brackets. The question statements have also been denoted with a variable value.

2 Participant Data

2.1 Age

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your age?	0.00	67.00	27.62	12.21	149.19	346

2.2 Gender

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Male	14.62%	50
2	Female	74.56%	255
3	Non-binary / third gender	6.43%	22
4	Prefer not to say	4.39%	15
	Total	100%	342

2.3 Citizenship

#	Answer	%	Count
1	EU	85.93%	281
2	Non-EU	9.48%	31
3	Prefer not to say	4.59%	15
	Total	100%	327

2.4 Education

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#	Answer	%	Count
1	Early childhood education ('less than primary' for educational attainment)	0.00%	0
2	Primary education	2.96%	9
3	Lower secondary education	5.59%	17
4	Upper secondary education	25.00%	76
5	Post-secondary non-tertiary education	6.91%	21
6	Short-cycle tertiary education	6.91%	21
7	Bachelor's or equivalent level	30.92%	94
8	Master's or equivalent level	16.78%	51
9	Doctorate or equivalent level	3.29%	10
10	Not elsewhere classified	1.64%	5
	Total	100%	304

2.5 Professions

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#	Answer	%	Count
1	Writer	13.20%	54
2	Visual Artist/Designer	62.84%	257
3	Crafter	11.74%	48
4	Performer/Musician	8.07%	33
5	Actor/Director	4.16%	17
	Total	100%	409

2.6 Profession based on Earnings

3 Conclusion

3.1 Survey

This questionnaire has been developed to understand the experience of creators and performing artists with recent developments such as the emergence of digital platforms, artificial intelligence, the covid pandemic and general issues concerning copyright, piracy and the impact of these developments on your earnings. It is important to understand the impact these issues have on artists to make better policies for the creative sector. The survey is part of the project reCreating Europe (<https://www.recreating.eu/>) and is commissioned by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Program (Grant agreement No. 870626). The survey is delivered by a research team at the Institute for Information Law (IViR), University of Amsterdam (UvA), The Netherlands.

Your input is very valuable for our research project. We hope that you spend some of your precious time to complete the survey. If you agree to take part in the study, please complete the consent form on the next page. You remain free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason.

If you have any questions about reCreating Europe, do not hesitate to ask the Consortium members and visit www.recreating.eu for further information on the project's privacy policies. For any further information about this survey, you can contact us at a.pervaiz@uva.nl. Thank you very much for your participation!

Abeer Pervaiz, Postdoctoral Researcher
Joost Poort, Associate Professor

Variable: Consent_Form

I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study. I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind. I understand that my personal data will be processed as stated in the privacy information.

For further details please click [GDPR](#)

- I agree to participate (1)
- I disagree to participate (2)

Variable: Captcha

Before you proceed to the survey please complete the captcha below.

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Demographics

In this section we ask a few questions about yourself.

What is your age?

Variable: Age

What is your gender?

Variable: Gender

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - Non-binary / third gender (3)
 - Prefer not to say (4)
-

Where do you currently live?

Variable: Country

Country (1)

▼ Afghanistan (1) ... Other (240)

What is your citizenship?

Variable: Citizenship

- EU (1)
 - Non-EU (2)
 - Prefer not to say (3)
-

What is your nationality?**Variable: Nationality**

Nationality (1)

Please indicate the number of people in your household (including yourself).**Variable: Household**

What is your highest level of education?**Variable: Education**

- Early childhood education ('less than primary' for educational attainment) (1)
- Primary education (2)
- Lower secondary education (3)
- Upper secondary education (4)
- Post-secondary non-tertiary education (5)
- Short-cycle tertiary education (6)
- Bachelor's or equivalent level (7)
- Master's or equivalent level (8)
- Doctorate or equivalent level (9)
- Not elsewhere classified (10)

What is your first language?**Variable: Language**

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Language (1)

▼ Afrikaans (1) ... Other (73)

Professional Career

Variable: Professional_Career

In this section you will be asked some questions about your professional occupation. We distinguish three categories of work creators and performers may be engaged in:

Variable: CW

i. Creative work: your core creative activities. For example, professionally you introduce yourself as a graphic designer or as an actor.

Variable: AW

ii. Arts related work: activities that are related to your creative work. For example, you are professionally a musician and you also work as a music teacher.

Variable: Non_AW

iii. Non-arts related work: activities that are unrelated to your creative and arts-related work. For example, working as a bar tender, taxi driver, consultant etc.

Which of the following professions best describes your creative work as an artist? Multiple answers can be given. From those answers sub-categories will follow.

Variable: Prof_Writer

- Writer (1)

Variable: Prof_VAD

- Visual Artist/Designer (2)

Variable: Prof_Crafter

- Crafter (3)

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music

- Performer/Musician (4)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director

- Actor/Director (5)

Writer

- Author (21)

Variable: Writer_Author

- Translator (literary,artistic) (22)

Variable: Writer_Translator

- Playwriter (23)

Variable: Writer_Playwriter

- Screenwriter (24)

Variable: Writer_Screenwriter

- Lyricist (writes words only) (25)

Variable: Writer_Lyricist

- Songwriter (writes and compose) (26)

Variable: Writer_Songwriter

- Composer (27)

Variable: Writer_Composer

- Biographer (28)

Variable: Writer_Biographer

- Journalist (29)

Variable: Writer_Journalist

- Other (30) _____

Variable: Writer_Other

Visual Artist/Designer

- Graphic Designer (1)

Variable: VAD_Graphic Deisgner

- Painter (2)

Variable: VAD_Painter

- Sculptor (3)

Variable: VAD_Sculptor

- Printmaker (4)

Variable: VAD_Printmaker

- Drawer (5)

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Variable: VAD_Drawer

- Photographer (6)

Variable: VAD_Photographer

- Game Designer (7)

Variable: VAD_Game Designer

- Graffiti Artist (8)

Variable: VAD_Graffiti Artist

- Tattoo/Henna Artist (9)

Variable: VAD_Tattoo/Henna Artist

- Fashion Designer (10)

Variable: VAD_Fashion Designer

- Illustrator (11)

Variable: VAD_Illustrator

- Cartoonist (12)

Variable: VAD_Cartoonist

- Architect (13)

Variable: VAD_Architect

- Calligraphy Artist (14)

Variable: VAD_Calligraphy Artist

- Other (15) _____

Variable: VAD_Other

Crafter

- Pottery maker (9)

Variable: Crafter_Pottery maker

- Resin artist (10)

Variable: Crafter_Resin artist

- Ceramic artist (11)

Variable: Crafter_Ceramic artist

- Jewelry designer (12)

Variable: Crafter_ Jewelry designer

- Floral designer (13)

Variable: Crafter_ Floral designer

- Glass blower (14)

Variable: Crafter_ Glass blower

- Woodworker (15)

Variable: Crafter_ Woodworker

- Other (16) _____

Variable: Crafter_ Other

Performer/Musician

- Dancer (1)

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music_Dancer

- Singer (2)

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music_Singer

- Musician (3)

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music_Musician

- Choreographer (4)

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music_Choreographer

- Comedian (5)

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music_Comdian

- Puppet player (6)

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music_Puppet player

- Other (7) _____

Variable: Prof_Perfom_Music_Other

Actor/Director

- Live stage actor (1)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_LS actor

- Film actor (2)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_Film actor

- Television actor (3)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_TV actor

- TV commercial actor (4)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_TVC actor

- Theatre director (5)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_Theater director

- Film director (6)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_Film director

- Voice over actor (7)

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_VOA

- Other (8) _____

Variable: Prof_Actor_Director_Other

Which of these professions is most important for you in terms of earnings?

- Author (1)
- Translator (literary, artistic) (2)
- Playwriter (3)
- Screenwriter (4)
- Lyricist (writes words only) (5)
- Songwriter (writes and compose) (6)
- Composer (7)
- Biographer (8)
- Journalist (9)
- $\{Q17/ChoiceTextEntryValue/30\}$ (10)
- Graphic Designer (11)
- Painter (12)

- Sculptor (13)
- Printmaker (14)
- Drawer (15)
- Photographer (16)
- Game Designer (17)
- Graffiti Artist (18)
- Tattoo/Henna Artist (19)
- Fashion Designer (20)
- Illustrator (21)
- Cartoonist (22)
- Architect (23)
- Calligraphy Artist (24)
- [\\${Q18/ChoiceTextEntryValue/15}](#) (25)
- Pottery maker (26)
- Resin artist (27)
- Ceramic artist (28)
- Jewellery designer (29)
- Floral designer (30)
- Glass blower (31)
- Woodworker (32)
- [\\${Q19/ChoiceTextEntryValue/16}](#) (33)
- Dancer (34)
- Singer (35)
- Musician (36)
- Choreographer (37)
- Comedian (38)
- Puppet player (39)
- [\\${Q20/ChoiceTextEntryValue/7}](#) (40)
- Live stage actor (41)
- Film actor (42)
- Television actor (43)
- TV commercial actor (44)
- Theatre director (45)

- Film director (46)
- Voice over actor (47)
- $\{Q21/ChoiceTextEntryValue/8\}$ (48)

How can your current career stage as an artist best be described?

Variable: Current_Artist Career

- Beginning/Starting out (1)
- Becoming established (2)
- Established (3)
- Retired (4)

Have you had any type of training for your creative work?

Variable: CW_Training

- Formal training (1)
- Self-taught/Learning on the job (2)
- Other training (3) _____

What percentage of your income do you derive from your creative work? Please give an estimate.

Variable: CW_Income_%

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
%	0.00	100.00	32.21	35.40	1252.91	258

How many hours do you spend on your creative, arts related and non-arts related work in an average week? Please select.

	0 (1)	1-11 (2)	12-23 (3)	24-35 (4)	36-40 (5)	41 or more (6)
Creative work (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Variable: CW_Hrs						
Arts related work (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Variable: AW_Hrs						
Non-arts related work (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Variable: Non_Aw_Hrs						

How many hours per week would you like to spend on your creative work?

	0 (1)	1-11 (2)	12-23 (3)	24-35 (4)	36-40 (5)	41 or more (6)
Creative work (1)	<input type="radio"/>					

What is the reason that you are unable to spend more time on your creative work?
Variable: CW_Time

	I have to spend time on arts related or non-arts work to make a living (1)	There are not enough work opportunities for me (2)	Personal reasons (3)
Strongly disagree (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagree (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Somewhat disagree (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neither agree nor disagree (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Somewhat agree (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agree (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strongly Agree (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Collective Management Organizations (CMOs)

In this section you will be asked some questions about your experience with Collective Management Organizations (CMOs).

A **collective management organisation** is an organisation which is authorised to manage copyright or rights related to copyright on behalf of multiple rightholders for their collective benefit and is owned or controlled by its members or organised on a not-for-profit basis

Are you registered with one or more Collective Management Organizations (CMOs)?
Variable: CMO_Registered

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

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Which of the following reasons best explains why you are not registered with any CMO?

Variable: CMO_Not_Registered

- I am not aware of CMO's relevant to my field/creative activity (1)
 - I find no benefits of registering with any CMO (2)
 - I find the process of registering with a CMO confusing or difficult (3)
 - Prefer not to answer/Don't Know (4)
-

Which CMO you are registered with is most relevant for your earnings?

Variable: CMO_Earnings

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: CMO_Services

	\${Q32/ChoiceTextEntryValue} is important for my income generation (1)	\${Q32/ChoiceTextEntryValue} helps me in enforcing my rights (2)	\${Q32/ChoiceTextEntryValue} offers me good advice related to my work and supports me by looking after my interests (3)	\${Q32/ChoiceTextEntryValue} is sufficiently transparent in it's payment to me (4)
Strongly disagree (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagree (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Somewhat disagree (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neither agree nor disagree (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Somewhat agree (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agree (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strongly Agree (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Prefer not to say /Don't know (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Income/Earnings

In this section you will be asked questions related to your income/earnings.

What is the composition of your household or family?

Variable: Household

- Living alone (1)
 - Living alone with children living at home (2)
 - Living together / married without children living at home (3)
 - Living together / married with children living at home (4)
 - Live with parents or family (5)
 - Live in a residential group or student house (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

What is your financial role in the household?

Variable: Household_Finance

- I earn most of the household income (1)
 - My partner and I bring in about the same amount of income (2)
 - My partner contributes most of the household income (3)
-

Can you give an indication of your gross income for the year 2019 and the year 2020?

(This concerns your total income (creative work, arts related work, non-arts related work, grants, social assistance, unemployment benefits, etc.)

Variable: Gross_Income

	2019 (1)	2020 (2)
€0-10,000 (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
€11.000-20,000 (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
€21,000-40,000 (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
€41,000- 70,000 (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
€71,000-100,000 (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
€101,000-150,000 (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
€151,000-200,000 (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
€201,000 or more (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Prefer not to say/ Don't know (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Can you indicate whether your creative work income during the period 2015-2019 (before the COVID pandemic) had increased, decreased, or remained about the same?

Variable: CW_Income_Pre-Covid

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- Increased sharply (1)
 - Slightly increased (2)
 - About the same (3)
 - Slightly decreased (4)
 - Decreased sharply (5)
 - Prefer not to say/ Don't know (6)
-

Can you indicate whether your creative work income during the period 2019-2021 (since the COVID pandemic) had increased, decreased, or remained about the same?

Variable: CW_Income_Covid

- Increased sharply (1)
 - Slightly increased (2)
 - About the same (3)
 - Slightly decreased (4)
 - Decreased sharply (5)
 - Prefer not to say/ Don't know (6)
-

Which of the following are a source of income for you from your creative work? Multiple answers possible.

- Employment contracts (22)

Variable: Income_EC

- Freelancing/Self-Employed without employees (23)

Variable: Income_Freelance_SE

- Own business with employees (24)

Variable: Income_OB

- Remuneration/Receipts from CMOs (25)

Variable: Income_CMO

- Royalties (26)

Variable: Income_Royalties

- Passive Income (27)

Variable: Income_Passive

- Subsidies (28)

Variable: Income_Subsidies

- Grants/Prizes (29)

Variable: Income_Grants/Prizes

- Patrons /Donations (30)

Variable: Income_Patrons/Donations

- Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) (31)

Variable: Income_NFT

- Other (32) _____

Variable: Income_Other

Please indicate your earnings for each source of income in 2019.
(If you do not know the exact answer, please choose your best estimate. If you really have no idea, please choose 'Prefer not to say/Don't know'.)

	€ 0-10,000 (1)	€11,000-20,000 (2)	€21,000-40,000 (3)	€41,000-70,000 (4)	€71,000-100,000 (5)	€101,000-150,000 (6)	€151,000-200,000 (7)	€201,000 or more (8)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (9)
Employment contracts (1)	<input type="radio"/>								
Freelancing/Self-Employed without employees (2)	<input type="radio"/>								
Own business with employees (3)	<input type="radio"/>								
Remuneration/Receipts from CMOs (4)	<input type="radio"/>								
Royalties (5)	<input type="radio"/>								
Passive Income (6)	<input type="radio"/>								
Subsidies (7)	<input type="radio"/>								
Grants/Prizes (8)	<input type="radio"/>								
Patrons /Donations (9)	<input type="radio"/>								
Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) (10)	<input type="radio"/>								
{Q41/ChoiceTextEntryValue/32} (11)	<input type="radio"/>								

Digital Platforms

In this section you will be asked questions related to your experience with digital platforms.

Which of the following platforms have you used for your creative work. Multiple answers are possible.

Social Media Platforms

Variable: SMP

- Instagram (63)

Variable: SMP_Insta

- Facebook (64)

Variable: SMP_FB

- Twitter (65)

Variable: SMP_TW

- LinkedIn (66)

Variable: SMP_LIn

- Other (67) _____

Variable: SMP_Other

Media Sharing Platforms

Variable: MSP

- YouTube (73)

Variable: MSP_YT

- TikTok (74)

Variable: MSP_TikTok

- SnapChat (75)

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Variable: MSP_Snapchat

- Twitch (76)

Variable: MSP_Twitch

- Other (77) _____

Variable: MSP_Other

Music Streaming Platforms

Variable: MuSP

- Apple Music (69)

Variable: MuSP_AM

- Amazon Music Unlimited (68)

Variable: MuSP_AMU

- Deezer (70)

Variable: MuSP_Deezer

- Tidal (71)

Variable: MuSP_Tidal

- Spotify (72)

Variable: MuSP_Spotify

- YouTube Music (96)

Variable: MuSP_YTM

- Other (95) _____

Variable: MuSP_Other

Market Sharing Platforms

Variable: MarkSP

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- Etsy (78)

Variable: MarkSP_Etsy

- Domestika (79)

Variable: MarkSP_Dom

- Skillshare (80)

Variable: MarkSP_Skillshare

- Behance (81)

Variable: MarkP_Behance

- Amazon Handmade (82)

Variable: MarkSP_Amazon Handmade

- Other (83) _____

Variable: MarkSP_Other

Publishing Platforms

Variable: PSP

- Kindle Direct (84)

Variable: PSP_KinD

- Create Space (85)

Variable: PSP_Create Space

- iBooks (86)

Variable: PSP_iBooks

- Barnes & Noble Press (87)

Variable: PSP_iBooks

- Smashwords (88)

Variable: PSP_Smashwords

- Lulu (89)

Variable: PSP_Lulu

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- Wattpad (90)

Variable: PSP_Wattpad

- Substack (91)

Variable: PSP_Substack

- Other (92) _____

Variable: PSP_Other

Variable: Other_Platforms

- Other platforms (93) _____

Variable: Non_Platforms

- None of the above (97)

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: Platform_Sharing

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly Agree (7)	Prefer not to answer/Don't know (8)
I am aware of the terms of service of the platform I use to share my content over (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am informed and asked for my permission by the platform if they share, use or distribute my work (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am financially compensated for the work that is shared, used or distributed by the platform (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Platforms are transparent about the way payments are given out (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: Platform_Algoritims

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewh at agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongl y Agree (7)	Prefer not to answer/ Don't know (8)
I am aware of platform algorithms and how to use them for sharing of my content (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Algorithms can benefit beginning artists when it comes to sharing/recommendation of their content (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Algorithms can benefit established artists when it comes to sharing/recommendation of their content (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Algorithms help me in reaching my potential audience (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Can you indicate whether the income derived through digital platforms for you as an artist has increased, decreased, or has remained about the same during the period 2015-2019 (before the COVID pandemic)?

Variable: Income_DP_Pre Covid

- Increased sharply (1)
 - Slightly increased (2)
 - About the same (3)
 - Slightly decreased (4)
 - Decreased sharply (5)
 - Prefer not to say/ Don't know (6)
 - No income was generated (7)
-

Can you indicate whether the income derived through digital platforms for you as an artist has increased, decreased, or has remained about the same during the period 2019-2021 (since the COVID pandemic)?

Variable: Income_DP_Covid

- Increased sharply (1)
 - Slightly increased (2)
 - About the same (3)
 - Slightly decreased (4)
 - Decreased sharply (5)
 - Prefer not to say/ Don't know (6)
 - No income was generated (7)
-

Have you used ads for marketing your content?

Variable: Ads

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Have these ads led to any income generation?

Variable: Ads_Income

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Do you plan to use ads in the future?

Variable: Ads_Use

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Maybe (3)
 - I have not thought about it (4)
-

Has there been an occasion where your content was blocked, removed, demonetized, demoted or otherwise restricted by/on the platform?

Variable: DP_Content

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

**What was the reason given to you by the platform when your content was removed or demoted?
Multiple answers allowed.**

Variable: DP_Content_Reason

- Infringes the copyright or other rights of third parties (1)
- Infringes the terms of service of the platform (2)
- No reason was presented by the platform (3)
- Other (4) _____

Authors

Have you as an author self-published any work in the last 12 months?

Variable: Author

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Have you self-published a traditional (i.e. physical) work or an electronic publication?

Variable: Author_Publish

- Traditional Publication (1)
- Electronic Publication (2)
- Both (3)
- Other (4) _____

In comparison to the time before the COVID-19 pandemic, have you chosen an electronic publication more often?

Variable: Author_Elec_Publish

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

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In the last 12 months, have you paid towards self-publishing?

Variable: Author_Self_Pub

- Yes (please indicate amount in Euros) (1)

- No (2)
-

How are your royalties for print books calculated?

Variable: Author_Royalties_PB

- Percentage of retail / publisher's price (1)

- Percentage of net receipts (2)

- I do not receive royalties (3)

- I have not published print books (4)

- Other (5) _____
-

What is your usual royalty rate (%)?

Variable: Author_Royalty rate

- Hardback (1) _____

- Paperback (2) _____
-

How are your royalties for e-books calculated?**Variable: Authors_Royalties_Ebooks**

- Percentage of retail / publisher's price (1)
 - Percentage of net receipts (2)
 - I do not receive royalties (3)
 - I have not published e-books (4)
 - Other (5) _____
-

What is your usual royalty rate (%) on e-books provided by digital publishing platforms?**Variable: Authors_Royalties_Ebooks_PSP**_____

Have your royalty rates for e-books changed in the last 5 years?**Variable: Authors_Royalty rate_Ebooks**

- Increased sharply (1)
 - Slightly increased (2)
 - About the same (3)
 - Slightly decreased (4)
 - Decreased sharply (5)
 - Don't know / don't want to say (6)
-

Has your book/screenplay been converted into a movie by a streaming platform?

Variable: Author_MedSP

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Under process (3)
-

How much payment was offered to you in Euros?

Variable: Author_Payment_MedSP

End of Block: Authors

Start of Block: Music

In the last 12 months have you used streaming platforms to publish your music?

Variable: Music_MuSP

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

In which of the following ways were you able to publish on the streaming platform?

Variable: Music_MuSP_Publish

- Through a team member already having a membership of the streaming platform (1)
 - Through a distributor/provider (2)
 - Through a record label (3)
 - Through a manager (4)
 - As an independent artist (5)
 - Other (6) _____
-

In comparison to the time before the COVID-19 pandemic, have you increased your use of streaming platforms to publish your music?

Variable: Music_MuSP_Use_Pre Covid

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

In digital platform section you indicated the following streaming platforms as your method of distribution of your creative work. Out of this list please indicate which one is the most relevant for your income generation.

Variable: Music_MuSP_Income

- `#{Q97/ChoiceTextEntryValue/95}` (6)
 - YouTube Music (7)
 - Amazon Music Unlimited (1)
 - Apple Music (2)
 - Deezer (3)
 - Tidal (4)
 - Spotify (5)
-

How much do you receive per stream from $\${Q67/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}$?

Variable: Music_MuSP_Per Stream

- € 0-0.005 (1)
- € 0.006-0.010 (2)
- € 0.011-0.015 (3)
- €0.016-0.020 (4)
- Prefer not to say/Don't know (5)

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Some what disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to answer/Don't Know (8)
I am satisfied with the way <code>#{Q67/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoicesTextEntry}</code> compensates me for my work (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I generate enough revenue from <code>#{Q67/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoicesTextEntry}</code> (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the payment system of <code>#{Q67/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoicesTextEntry}</code> fair (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Variable: Music_MuSP_Compensation

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When it comes to distributing payments to artists, some streaming platforms use a pro-rata payment method. This method collects money from all users through subscriptions. This total amount is distributed to artists based on the total number of streams that each artist had, added over all subscribers.

Other streaming platforms use a user-centric payment system (UCPS). In this method, the budget available for artists is distributed per subscriber, based on his or her listening behaviour. For example, if a subscriber only listens to a single artist, the money available for distribution from this subscriber will all go to that artist. Based on this information you will be asked some questions regarding your opinion on these payment systems.

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: Music_MuSP_Payment system

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to answer/Don't Know (8)
The pro-rata payment system is a fair way of distribution of money to the artist (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The pro-rata payment system is beneficial for emerging artists (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The user-centric payment system is a fair way of distribution of money to the artist (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The user-centric payment system is beneficial for emerging artists (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Artificial Intelligence (AI)

In this section you will be asked questions related to your experience with Artificial Intelligence (AI).

How knowledgeable do you consider yourself regarding AI?

Variable: AI_Knowledge

- Not knowledgeable at all (1)
 - Slightly knowledgeable (2)
 - Moderately knowledgeable (3)
 - Very knowledgeable (4)
 - Extremely knowledgeable (5)
-

Do you find AI a threat or an opportunity for you?

Variable: AI_Threat/Opportunity

- Primarily a threat (1)
 - Primarily an opportunity (2)
 - Both (3)
 - Neither (4)
-

Have you ever used AI for creating your content?

Variable: AI_Content creation

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - No, but I plan to do so in the future (3)
-

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: AI_Impact

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)
I haven't used AI personally yet, but I expect to see a rise in my income if I implement it in my work (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I haven't used AI personally, but I expect to lose income because others are using it (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think artists using AI should have full authorship and protective rights of the content produced (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: AI_ Artist support

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)
AI has helped me expand my creativity (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI has helped me in saving time and creating more content (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI has helped me connect with the right audience (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI has brought a positive change in my income (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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As an artist
using AI, I
should
have full
authorship
and
protective
rights of
the content
produced
(5)

Piracy and Plagiarism

In this section you will be asked questions related to your experience with plagiarism and piracy.

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: PP_Content sharing

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	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)
Sharing of my content is fine as long as I am given due credit (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sharing of my content gives me more visibility and provides me opportunities (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sharing of my content is currently causing me financial loss (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I expect that sharing of my content will cause me financial loss in the future (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have experienced my content being used by other artists without my consent or by giving me any credit (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: PP_Action

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)
Harder action must be taken against those users who use my content without my permission (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Harder action must be taken against platforms/websites that use my content without giving me due credit (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Harder action must be taken against bigger brands that use my content without my permission (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: PP_Amateur artist competition

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)
I find the content produced by amateur artists a threat to my creative income (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find that amateur artists bring healthy competition for me as an artist (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Copyright

In this section you will be asked questions related to copyright.

How knowledgeable do you consider yourself regarding copyright?

Variable: ©_Knowledge

- Not knowledgeable at all (1)
 - Slightly knowledgeable (2)
 - Moderately knowledgeable (3)
 - Very knowledgeable (4)
 - Extremely knowledgeable (5)
-

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: ©_Protection

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)
Copyright is important for my professional work (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Copyright is important for my earnings (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Copyright protection should be stronger (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Copyright protection should be weaker (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often sign a contract transferring my copyright against my will (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often have disputes over copyright (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The Pandemic Impact

In this section you will be asked questions related to your experience with the COVID-19 pandemic.

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements:

Variable: Covid_CW_Impact

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/ Don't know (8)
COVID-19 caused me to find alternative ways to market my creative work and to find potential clients (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
COVID-19 caused me to lose clients (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
COVID-19 caused me to end my creative work (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
COVID-19 caused me to start working in a different creative field (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Did COVID-19 cause a change in the income generated through your creative work?**Variable: Covid_CW_Income**

- Increased sharply (1)
 - Slightly increased (2)
 - About the same / no change (3)
 - Slightly decreased (4)
 - Decreased sharply (5)
 - Don't know / don't want to say (6)
-

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements: The COVID-19 pandemic has...

Variable: Covid_CW_Earnings

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)	Prefer not to say/Don't know (8)
made it harder for me to earn as an artist (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
made it easier for me to earn as an artist (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
increased my earnings from digital modes of exploitation (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
increased the importance of copyright for my earnings (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Were you given any support from the government (funds/grants/subsidies etc)

Variable: Covid_Gov support

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - There was no government support (3)
 - I was not aware of any government support (4)
-

Can you give an estimate of the amount you received from the government in Euros?

Variable: Covid_Gov Support_Amount

To what extent did the amount you receive compensate you for your loss?

Variable: Covid_Compensation

- Fully (1)
 - Partially (2)
 - Not at all (3)
-

To what extent were you satisfied with the amount you received?

Variable: Covid_Compensation satisfaction

- Extremely dissatisfied (1)
- Somewhat dissatisfied (2)
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (3)
- Somewhat satisfied (4)
- Extremely satisfied (5)

We have reached the end of the survey. Would you like to give any feedback/suggestions? Please write briefly in the box below.

Would you be willing to be interviewed to further discuss your experience as an artist in relation to the survey or future research?

If **YES**, please submit your **name, email address and contact number** in the box below for us to contact you.

Your contact details will not be shared or distributed.

They will only be available to the researchers of this project and will not be used for other purposes than indicated above.

Note: The interview will be taken in **English**.

End of Survey

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